

BACHELOR OF ARTS IN MULTIMEDIA STUDIES
Capstone/Special Project

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

BACHELOR OF ARTS IN MULTIMEDIA STUDIES

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ON-THE-JOB TRAINING REPORT: UI/UX DESIGN INTERNSHIP

OJT Host Institution:

Universal Access And Systems Solutions Philippines Inc.

Duration of OJT:

19 August 2024 to 4 December 2024

Special Project Adviser:

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26 December 2024

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **LARYZE C. LOZANO** with the title: **“ON-THE-JOB TRAINING REPORT: UI/UX DESIGN INTERNSHIP”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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2 January 2025

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Biographical Sketch

Laryze Lozano is an aspiring multimedia artist from Quezon City, Philippines. After graduating from Eugenio Lopez Jr. Center for Media Arts Senior High School, she dedicated herself to honing her skills and passion in multimedia design.

Aside from being a full-time student, she enjoys taking on creative challenges and delving into new ideas. She likes to explore various forms of art, including traditional and digital drawing, graphic design, video editing, and user interface design. To gain more experience and expand her skills, she takes on internship projects focusing on graphic design and video production. Yet, her interest in both art and coding led her to discover a passion for UI/UX design, especially in website development, and thus, she decided to pursue a career in this field. An opportunity came when she was offered an internship in an IT company as a UI/UX designer and an opportunity to work as a freelancer, using the chance to also complete her special project for the BAMS program.

Outside her university and career, Laryze serves as the head of the Youth Ministry and Management Information System (MIS) Ministry at Jesus Is Lord Church, Tandang Sora Chapter. She often volunteers to create posters and designs for church events and inspires others as a preacher during Sunday services. Her leadership and creativity motivate her fellow youths to grow in their faith and discover their potential.

Acknowledgment

This special project is the result of countless sleepless nights, heartfelt prayers, tears, and, above all, the unwavering guidance, trust, and support of many wonderful people.

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Special thanks to Sir Joshua Rene Mariano, my OJT supervisor, for offering me this incredible internship opportunity and believing in my abilities. His valuable advice, unwavering support, and kindness boosted my confidence to complete all the projects and tasks during the internship. I am also grateful to the amazing team I have worked with at the Universal Access And Systems Solutions Philippines Inc,

whose warm attitude and constructive feedback made my OJT experience enjoyable and meaningful.

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SUMMARY

This report highlights the hands-on experience I gained while undergoing an on-the-job training (OJT) at Universal Access and Systems Solutions Philippines Inc., from August 19 to December 4, 2024. This OJT is one of the undertakings for my completion of the Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies degree program. The OJT aimed to bridge academic knowledge with practical application in multimedia design and development. My key tasks included creating user-centered and responsive UI/UX designs, prototyping with Figma, and developing functional web pages using tools like WebFlow. As a trainee, I contributed to real-world website design and development projects by addressing usability challenges, ensuring accessibility compliance, and implementing modern design standards, resulting in significant personal and professional growth.

Throughout my OJT, I explored and applied certain multimedia technologies and emerging trends in website development. These included leveraging AI-powered tools to optimize workflows and adhering to global accessibility standards like Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG). WCAG provides guidelines that will make web content accessible to a wider range of people, particularly to people with disabilities such as those with low vision, deafness, and cognitive limitations. It is a technical standard that is primarily intended for: "Web content developers", "web authoring tools", "web accessibility evaluation tool developers" and "others who want or need a standard for web accessibility, including for mobile accessibility". It follows four principles of accessibility: perceivable, operable, understandable, and robust. (Henry, 2024; Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.0, 2008)

Collaboration played a critical role, as I worked closely with supervisors and developers to align designs with project goals. Independent contributions, such as innovative design solutions and usability enhancements, further demonstrated my ability to balance technical requirements with creative problem-solving.

The OJT experience enhanced my skills in multimedia tools, advanced coding techniques, responsive design, and ethical considerations, and improved teamwork, communication, and adaptability. By addressing challenges and delivering professional outputs, I not only met the objectives of the program but also established a foundation for a career in multimedia design and development.

This report concludes with reflections on my experiences as well as with recommendations to enhance future OJT programs.

Laryze C. Lozano

I. INTRODUCTION

This report documents my activities, learnings, experiences, and reflections as an on-the-job trainee (OJT). My OJT is one of the activities conducted in partial fulfillment of my degree program, the Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies offered by the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU).

Purpose of the Report

The purpose of documenting my OJT experience is to reflect on the practical application of the theoretical knowledge in multimedia gained in the academic setting. This documentation also serves as a tool to evaluate learning outcomes and offers insights for future professional and personal development.

This report includes a description of the OJT, the weekly tasks, challenges faced, and project contributions and accomplishments achieved. It also highlights the trainee's use of multimedia, the techniques applied, and the soft and technical skills acquired during the internship.

Objectives of the OJT

The objectives of the OJT include the following:

1. To demonstrate and apply the theoretical knowledge and technical skills in multimedia development acquired from academic settings to the professional field.

2. To gain hands-on experience by working on real-world projects and to develop professional competencies such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills in a professional setting.
3. To explore and learn emerging multimedia technologies and trends, including responsive design, accessibility standards, and user-centric methodologies.

Significance of OJT in Career Development

The OJT is crucial for the development of multimedia students' skills, design thinking, and competencies relevant to the professional field, and bridges the gap between theory and practice. Students will gain valuable experience by working on projects, collaborating with a team, and communicating with the client and stakeholders. They will also gain valuable insight into their abilities and have the opportunity to enhance their skills through feedback from industry professionals.

By reflecting on their accomplishments and evaluating their tasks, they can identify areas for improvement. This process not only builds their confidence but also equips them to excel in their chosen career path.

In the local setting, the OJT helps adapt to the region-specific user preference and cultural nuances, ensuring that the design or digital product they produce would be impactful and relevant. In the localization of a digital product, the designer or creator must understand and meet the target audience's cultural, linguistic, and

behavioral preferences to enhance user-centric design and functionality according to their needs.

In a global context, OJT introduces multimedia interns to emerging technologies like AI and user-centric design trends, equipping them with techniques, protocols, and methods used worldwide. This prepares them to compete in the global market and contribute to multimedia development initiatives.

II. PROFILE OF THE OJT HOST INSTITUTION

Company Background

The OJT was conducted at the Universal Access Systems and Solutions Inc. (UAS), which is a forward-thinking company dedicated to empowering organizations by providing agile and evolving IT solutions that shape and support communities since 2005. With their professionals with more than 20 years of experience in information technology, they bring technological innovative solutions that bring people and technology together and help various companies thrive with new technology. Over the years, their partners have recognized them, driven by their four founding pillars: Best-of-breed IT infrastructure, enterprise solutions, pure fiber connectivity, and managed services.

They are committed to shaping communities “through agile and evolving solutions that provide profitable and cost-efficient platforms for the future of our people” and a vision to provide “access to success-driving technology” to all organizations through their service-oriented services. Their services and products include IT infrastructure solutions, software solutions, cabling and connectivity, managed services, and industry solutions.

OJT Supervisor Details

The OJT program was supervised by Mr. Joshua Rene Mendez Mariano, a Development Networks Engineer in the Business Innovation & Digital Solutions Department.

As an OJT supervisor, he coordinated with UPOU regarding my tasks and responsibilities in the institutions. He introduced me to emerging multimedia technologies and trends utilized in UAS.

Organizational Multimedia Initiatives

The Universal Access Systems and Solutions Inc. (UAS) utilizes emerging multimedia technologies to deliver software solutions. The UAS design team uses tools like Adobe Creative Suite to create designs and other media products for promotional purposes and assets for websites and systems. As for software developers, UAS uses Visual Studio Code, XAMPP, Github, and Gitbash. Aside from HTML and CSS, the institution utilizes the Laravel framework, Javascript Vanilla, JQuery, PHP, and other available languages apart from HTML and CSS.

When it comes to UI/UX design and front-end development, online libraries for fonts, color themes, CSS components libraries (e.g. Flowbyte, Tailwind, and Bootstrap), and icon libraries (e.g. Heroicons) were used. For building websites or application systems, platforms such as WebFlow, WordPress, and Microsoft Power

Apps were utilized as they require less code and have ready-built sections and templates for websites, making the work faster and easier.

Due to the UAS' nature of work, the company also adopted collaboration platforms for team activities and meetings such as Webex, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, and other cloud-based productivity and collaboration tools.

UAS Protocols and Standard

At the start of each project, the institution prioritizes defining the company's brand design, including its color palette, font style, and overall design approach, to ensure consistency across all platforms. They strive to create modern, intuitive designs while maintaining alignment with the company's branding guidelines.

In terms of functionality, they emphasize responsiveness, adaptability to all screen sizes, accessibility, and user-centricity, adhering to established standards for website and application user interfaces.

Each phase of the project is documented, including the user journey/story, which serves as a guide to help both owners and users navigate the site or application effectively. Once developers complete the site's pages, including design and functionality, the project undergoes Quality Assurance (QA) and User Acceptance Testing (UAT) to ensure it meets quality standards before being officially deployed.

Integration of Innovative Multimedia Trends

As an IT solutions company, they encourage their team to adopt innovative trends that enhance work quality while ensuring flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and efficiency. AI-powered tools, such as AI chatbots (e.g., ChatGPT), assist developers with coding. Additionally, AI-integrated Dynamic Content Management Systems (CMS) on custom website platforms, like WebFlow, enable developers to create and manage content with little to no coding. Platforms like WebFlow and WordPress also offer integration options and custom code support, providing flexibility and extending functionality for developers.

III. TRAINING PROGRAM DESCRIPTION

The UAS requires its trainee to render 600 hours of work. I reported to the Business Innovation and Digital Solutions Department from 19 August to 4 December 2024; Monday to Friday, for 8 hours each day.

Responsibilities and Duties

My main responsibility was to create and present an interactive and modern interface design for the revamp of the company's website under the supervision of the assigned UAS team. I also communicated constantly with the stakeholders to ensure that project objectives were met. My responsibilities and duties involve the following:

Create UI/UX designing and prototyping for the main website on the website transfer project. This included researching user needs, defining clear objectives, and collaborating with the stakeholders to gather requirements. The work also included creating wireframes, developing an interactive prototype in Figma, and ensuring the design is visually appealing while enhancing user engagement and experience on the website, aligning with the project objectives.

Learn basic HTML/CSS and conduct lab exercises for assessment. This involved understanding the basic structures of styling web pages, covering topics on HTML elements, attributes, and CSS properties,

and applying these concepts in practical lab exercises for assessment to gauge an understanding and proficiency in HTML/CSS.

Create improvements in the user interface on currently deployed websites and applications. It included analyzing user feedback and performance metrics to identify areas of enhancements on the currently deployed website. The process also involved enhancing the user interface for better experience and engagement, improving and updating the visual design, and ensuring consistency and intuitive user experience across all devices.

Learn Webflow platform and Laravel framework. It involved understanding functionalities and applications. For Webflow, it involves mastering content management, CMS, and building web pages. For Laravel, it involves learning its MVC architecture, routing and database management.

Attend website transfer alignment meetings. I actively participated in discussions and collaborated with the team to ensure project goals, timelines, and requirements were met. This includes clarifying design and functionality expectations, addressing technical considerations, and coordinating tasks effectively.

Daily activity reporting. It involved documenting, reporting, and summarizing tasks, progress, and achievements accomplished within a workday.

Bi-Weekly Report Summary

Weeks 1 and 2 (August 19 - August 30, 2024)

- Aligned project objectives, assigned tasks, gathered requirements and set timelines.
- Conducted online meetings with stakeholders, and collaborated with the design and development teams.
- Worked on wireframing and prototyping Phase 1 of the UAS website pages (Contact, About, and Careers) in Figma.
- Presented initial designs for feedback and approval.

Weeks 3 and 4 (September 2 – September 13, 2024)

- Finalized Phase 1 designs for the About page and started Phase 2 layouts (Home, Solutions/Services, and Insights).
- Reviewed layouts to ensure prototype functionality met requirements and collaborated with the front-end developer to align designs and integrate feedback.
- Styled Contact and Careers pages in WebFlow as part of the front-end development training and refined button designs.

Weeks 5 and 6 (September 16 – September 27, 2024)

- Designed phone screen layouts for the Milestones and Job Opportunity sections and layout concepts for the Case Studies and Terms and Conditions pages.

- Enhanced the Certification section on the About page using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript in CodePen.
- Built Terms and Conditions, Insights, and Solutions pages and embedded the "Our Commitment" section in WebFlow.
- Held collaborative meetings on project updates (e.g., privacy policies, Makati Health Department project) and progress reviews with Ms. Nadine.
- Improved technical skills in CSS grid, flexbox, and JavaScript.

Weeks 7 and 8 (September 30 - October 11, 2024)

- Signed the contract for the Makati Health Department (MHD) project and attended multiple synchronous meetings.
- Progressed in the UAS website in WebFlow: added CMS details, improved responsiveness, implemented social links, and revised content.
- Prepared for the MHD project by learning Bootstrap, installing Composer and Laravel, and setting up the environment.

Week 9 and 10 (October 14 - October 25, 2024)

- Developed Phase 1 front-end for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code, styling admin and user pages.
- Enhanced UAS website back-end: implemented email systems, added CMS for Employee Highlights, and documented user stories.

- Attended MHD-QMS progress meetings and a mid-OJT evaluation with my research adviser at UPOU, Prof. Luisa Gelisan, and OJT supervisor, Sir Joshua Mariano, to discuss progress and the final report

Week 11 and 12 (October 28 - November 8, 2024)

- Designed and styled Job Opportunity and Case Study pages for the UAS website in Figma and WebFlow.
- Improved UAS website responsiveness, fixed animations, and edited content.
- Enhanced responsiveness for MHD-QMS account pages (Master Admin, Health Validator, Patient) in Visual Studio Code.
- Added CMS details for solutions in the MHD-QMS project.
- Attended an MHD project update meeting and observed a holiday.

Week 13 and 14 (November 11 - November 22, 2024)

- Progress of UAS website includes: QA testing to ensure functionality and design quality.
- Started writing the final report for the MMS 200 Special Project.
- Discussed final OJT requirements with Sir Kevin, including obtaining my certificate and evaluation form.
- Attended a synchronous meeting with the UAS team to focus on the UI/UX design of the Workforce Tracker System.
- Set up my UAS email on Outlook, requested app access, and evaluated the app's layout and design.

Week 15 & 16 (November 25 - December 4, 2024)

- Completed 64 hours, reaching a total of 600 OJT hours.
- Finalized UI designs for the UAS Workforce Tracker System in Figma, including light and dark versions.
- Progressed to 60% completion on the OJT Final Report for the MMS 200 Special Project.
- Progressed of the UAS website: User Acceptance Testing (UAT) for ensuring readiness for deployment.

IV. SKILLS, KNOWLEDGE, AND TECHNIQUES ACQUIRED

Multimedia Technology and Techniques

Range and Use

During the internship, I was able to use a variety of multimedia technologies and tools. Figma was utilized for creating wireframes, prototypes, and collaborative design work, while also exploring essential UI/UX tools such as icon libraries and UI components. Additionally, I was introduced to WebFlow, a no/low-code web-building platform for creating dynamic websites, which also supports collaboration and web hosting. Visual Studio Code, a free code editor platform, was also employed for writing and debugging basic HTML and CSS for the project. Its features include a vast extension ecosystem, built-in coding assistance, debugging tools, live previews, customizable themes, and seamless integration with other tools (Visual Studio Code, n.d.).

Emerging Trends and Protocols

In developing the project, key multimedia trends such as AI chatbots (e.g. ChatGPT) were utilized to assist the front-end developers in writing codes making the work faster and easier. Flexible CMS with AI-generated content is also one of the trends when it comes to no/less code website builders, allowing developers to generate temporary content with just a few clicks.

Working on real-world projects, I was familiarized with design systems, that ensure consistency across interfaces, responsiveness, and accessibility protocols, thus designs comply with WCAG for inclusivity.

Additionally, there were procedures employed by the institution before a completed website was deployed. These are Quality Assurance Testing (QAT) and User Acceptance Testing (UAT). QA Testing is the “final quality-control gate” that the website must pass through to locate and describe software defects or bugs in the system; the defects or bugs shall be fixed by the developers ensuring functionality, and validating that the final deliverable performs as expected (Strauss & Hogan, 2013). User Acceptance Testing, also called beta testing or end-user testing, refers to the stage of product development where end users evaluate it to ensure it meets their requirements and real-world needs. This is considered a critical step in validating that the final product is ready for deployment (Stanford University IT, n.d.)

Technical Proficiency

Hardware and Software Skills

Through my OJT, I enhanced my proficiency in using Figma, including building complex components, maintaining responsive layouts, and prototyping with animations and triggers. I also gained hands-on experience with WebFlow's functionality, such as its CMS, and Visual Studio Code by collaborating with the front-end developer to build pages. Furthermore, I had deeper understanding on the utilization of browser's Developer/Inspect tool, allowing me to check responsiveness,

identify code errors, and make temporary edits to live page content and design. This streamlined processes and minimized trial-and-error adjustments.

New Technologies

I explored various Figma plugins, including the Figma to Webflow plugin, which streamlined the transition from design to development. I also learned to use Webflow Logic to automate workflows and integrate Webflow with e-commerce platforms like Mailchimp for email marketing and Zapier for seamless app automation. On the development side, I used Git Bash to install Composer, a dependency management tool, and gained hands-on experience setting up and managing PHP frameworks by installing Laravel 7 locally.

Soft Skills

Collaboration and Independence

As an OJT trainee, I undertook various tasks independently, including creating design concepts and prototyping on Figma for UI designs, which enhanced my problem-solving skills while considering the deadline for each phase. Aside from these, I actively engaged in discussions with the front-end developer and supervisor, working closely with them on translating designs into code and proposing design solutions to the team during brainstorming sessions, to help refine the overall design concept. I took responsibility for implementing the team's feedback into the design while actively incorporating colleagues' ideas to enhance the visual consistency of the final product.

Feedback Utilization

The feedback from my supervisor significantly enhanced my skills and understanding of the UI/UX design process. My awareness of user needs was reinforced and it improved my ability to create designs that are flexible and adaptable to smaller screen sizes, ultimately enhancing both usability and design quality. This experience also helped me clearly define objectives and requirements while distinguishing between what is feasible and what is not within a project's constraints. Additionally, through my supervisor's advice, I learned to document the color palette, font library, CSS styles, and icon libraries used in UI design to serve as a reference style guide for front-end developers. This process gave me a deeper understanding of the critical questions UI/UX designers must ask to align designs with user needs and technical constraints.

VI. APPLICATION OF EMERGING TRENDS AND KNOWLEDGE CREATION

Practical Application

I actively applied emerging multimedia trends, protocols, and procedures in various projects. For example, I utilized the Figma to Webflow plugin to streamline the transition from design to development, aligning with the trend of automation in the design workflow and also utilized ChatGPT to write codes efficiently.

Additionally, I incorporated responsive design techniques to ensure designs were adaptable to different screen sizes, addressing usability trends and standards. Using VS Code and Bootstrap, I was able to refine CSS styling and improve the responsiveness of specific web pages, following best practices in front-end development. These applications provided a practical, hands-on approach to utilizing modern multimedia tools while adhering to established protocols, resulting in efficient and user-centric design solutions.

Knowledge Creation

New Multimedia Knowledge Product

I have created an interactive design prototype using Figma, tailored for a user-onboarding flow that spanned desktop, tablet, and mobile screens. This product integrates responsive design principles and modern UI elements, ensuring flexibility and usability across devices and making it more intuitive and tailored to user preferences, which is increasingly essential in multimedia design. By applying multimedia tools such as Figma plugins and Webflow Logic, the prototype

demonstrated how emerging technologies can streamline workflows and improve user engagement. This work is highly relevant to the field, as it showcases the importance of integrating design and development processes for efficient project delivery.

Research Contribution

I help refine multimedia processes by exploring cross-platform design-to-development workflows. By experimenting with tools such as Figma to Webflow plugins and automation platforms like Zapier, I was able to highlight methods to reduce manual handoff errors and improve productivity. This practical exploration contributes to multimedia theories by validating how automated workflows can enhance design efficiency and promote consistency between design and development teams.

Local/Global Initiative Contribution

Working on local multimedia projects that address global challenges, such as the need for accessible and responsive design, allowed me to enhance user interfaces tailored to individual needs in the local community. By ensuring the designs adhered to WCAG and focusing on mobile-first development, I contributed to addressing global issues of digital inclusivity and usability. Additionally, by integrating automation tools like Mailchimp and Zapier, scalable solutions for small businesses are provided, helping them compete in the global digital economy while bridging the gap between local needs and international standards.

VII. CHALLENGES, PROBLEM-SOLVING, AND ADAPTABILITY

Challenges Faced

a. Balancing aesthetic vs. functionality

One of the most challenging aspects of UI design was striking the balance between a visually appealing design and functional usability. A design may look innovative and interactive, but if it sacrifices usability or creates confusion, it can lead to a poor user experience.

b. Improving usability features

Prioritizing user-centered design must ensure that the UI/UX developer also understands users' behavior in using the elements to achieve their goals. To improve usability, I must ensure that critical design elements such as pagination, contrast, buttons, and alternative navigation options are functional and distinguishable from decorative design. These adjustments often require careful consideration to enhance user interaction while maintaining simplicity.

c. Lengthy Terms & Conditions and Privacy Policy:

One consideration in designing a website is the lengthy terms and conditions and privacy policy that is critical for addressing user trust issues but is too complex and lengthy to read. Simplifying these without losing necessary legal details presents a design and communication challenge.

d. Interactive yet professional design

Integrating interactivity and animations (e.g., Our Commitment section) while maintaining a professional tone was also challenging. As a UI/UX designer, one should know when to use animations and interactivity without overusing them to avoid distracting users.

e. Design flexibility for multiple screens:

One of the difficult challenges I encountered in the design process was creating a flexible and responsive design for diverse devices (e.g., mobile, tablet, desktop) while achieving consistency without compromising design quality.

f. Balancing innovative vs. familiar design

Pushing for innovation may lead to designs that users find unfamiliar or difficult to navigate. Although I had a lot of innovative ideas, I also balanced them with familiar elements to prevent confusing users and other developers who translated the design into code. (ex. Milestone Section)

g. WebFlow technical limitations

While Webflow is a powerful tool for creating responsive designs, it has its limitations when it comes to complex customizations. For instance, implementing advanced functionality or custom scripts can be challenging due to Webflow's

predefined structure and lack of full-code flexibility which poses as a constraint to the design.

h. Installing and Setting Up the Environment for PHP, Laravel, and Composer

Part of the OJT program required me to familiarize myself with back-end applications to deliver better and more functional designs. I encountered issues in setting up a backend environment with PHP, Laravel, and Composer, such as incorrect configurations or compatibility problems with the system.

Problem-Solving Approaches

To overcome UI/UX design challenges, I took the following approaches:

- To enhance user experience, without overwhelming the interface, the focus was creating clean, minimalistic layouts and introducing innovative elements only in specific sections. With this, the digital product will retain its uniqueness and professionalism with its innovative design plus using familiar elements for easier navigation. Simple designs are flexible and easily adaptable to various devices.
- To identify what is best for users by experimenting with new design approaches and usability features while conducting usability tests. This requires constant iteration and independent research, which also

addresses the problem with the responsiveness of the design, innovation, and interactivity.

- To refine and improve design iterations, feedback from the supervisor and team members through the testing phases was gathered. This is critical for improving the design.
- To develop and propose solutions aimed at improving the overall functionality and ease of use, grounded in user-centered design principles.
- To apply established design principles for guided decision-making and ensuring designs align with best practices. Design principles from “Universal Principles of Design” (Lindwel et al., 2010) were applied in the design process.
 - Hick’s Law - It states that decision-making time increases with the number and complexity of choices, emphasizing the need for simplicity in design.
 - Fitts's Law - It highlights that larger and closer targets are quicker and easier to interact with, guiding optimal placement and sizing of interface elements.
 - Miller's Law - This states that people can hold about seven (± 2) items in their working memory, encouraging information to be grouped into manageable chunks.

- Affordance - It refers to design elements that suggest their functionality, such as a button appearing clickable, ensuring intuitive interactions.
 - Constraints - Limit user actions to prevent errors and guide behavior.
 - Jakob's Law - It underscores the importance of familiar design patterns, as users expect systems to behave like others they've used, reducing learning curves.
 - Aesthetic-usability effect - This shows that visually appealing designs are perceived as easier and more satisfying to use.
- To familiarize oneself with the capabilities and limitations of tools like WebFlow and other design applications. This helped in ensuring whether the UI/UX design was feasible within the constraints of multimedia tools. This approach also saves time by reducing trial and error, as it allows for informed decision-making during the design process.
 - To apply the design thinking process – empathize, define, ideate, prototype, and test (ideo.org). Approaching design as an iterative process, continuously testing and refining based on usability insights and project objectives.

- To tackle technical limitations with a flexible mindset, exploring alternative solutions, and utilizing available resources to overcome challenges effectively.

Adaptability

When faced with unexpected findings or changes, I reevaluated the original plan and prioritized areas needing immediate attention. Feedback from the supervisor and team members guided the iterative refinements, ensuring designs aligned with project goals, while usability testing insights led to expanded scenarios and prototype adjustments. The limitations in tools like WebFlow prompted me to explore alternative solutions or workflows. Learning new techniques, maintaining open communication, and refining the process dynamically, helped me ensure that the project remained on track without compromising quality or functionality.

VII. CONTRIBUTIONS AND ACCOMPLISHMENTS

Organizational Contributions

I significantly contributed to the company's goals by working on multimedia initiatives that enhanced both the design and development processes. This involved designing responsive UI prototypes in Figma for key projects, ensuring consistent user experiences across desktop, tablet, and mobile platforms. I also improved the company's web presence by building and optimizing specific web pages in Webflow, prioritizing responsiveness and usability, aligning with the company's goal of delivering modern and accessible digital solutions.

Personal Accomplishments

I successfully completed the following tasks:

- Developing wireframes, prototypes and designs for various projects using Figma, in particular for the revamp of the UAS website.
- Introducing innovative ideas to design problems encountered and in improving user experience.
- Updating and communicating with the team about the progress of website development.
- Enhancing web page responsiveness for the UAS website in WebFlow and for Makati Health Department - Queuing Management System using Bootstrap and CSS customizations.

- Contributing to front-end development by building certain pages and sections in WebFlow for the UAS website. (e.g Contact, Solutions, Insights, and Terms and Conditions pages)
- Learning about UI components and interactive elements in Flowbite CSS, Bootstrap, Javascript, and advanced CSS.

I demonstrated proficiency in multimedia tools such as Figma, Webflow, and VS Code, while applying industry standards like WCAG to ensure accessibility.

There was positive feedback from the team for my independent contributions, particularly the user onboarding flow prototype, which was praised for its clarity and adaptability. My ability to create user-centered design solutions, meet project objectives, and integrate multimedia technologies effectively was also acknowledged. Additionally, I was commended for my confidence in HTML and CSS, for completing tasks and deliverables ahead of deadlines, and for maintaining clear and effective communication with team members.

These accomplishments reflect my strong understanding and application of multimedia technologies, contributing to both my personal growth and the attainment of the institution's objectives.

VIII. EVALUATION OF THE OJT EXPERIENCE

Achievement of Objectives

During my OJT, I successfully achieved the initial objectives, particularly those focused on enhancing my multimedia knowledge and skills. I effectively applied theoretical knowledge from academic settings to practical projects, such as creating UI/UX designs and developing functional web pages using tools like Figma, WebFlow, and Visual Studio Code. I also met key objectives, including mastering responsive design, improving accessibility, and integrating innovative technologies. Additionally, I gained valuable experience in teamwork, communication, and user-centered design methodologies, delivering functional, visually appealing, and professional outputs.

Skill Development and Gaps

The OJT experience significantly improved my technical skills, such as creating responsive and adaptive designs, leveraging advanced features of Figma, and setting up environments for PHP and Laravel. I expanded my knowledge of industry trends, including AI-powered tools and WCAG accessibility standards. However, I identified areas for further improvement, such as mastering advanced coding techniques, streamlining workflows for greater efficiency, and addressing ethical challenges like simplifying privacy policies while maintaining compliance. I also recognized the need to enhance my knowledge of back-end development tools and strengthen my understanding of design evaluation processes.

Self-Assessment

Strengths and Weaknesses

My strengths include adaptability, creativity, teamwork, and the ability to effectively integrate feedback. I demonstrated proficiency in tools like Figma, WebFlow, and Bootstrap, as well as a strong commitment to user-centered design principles throughout the training. However, I need to improve my coding efficiency, master complex frameworks, and refine workflows to minimize trial and error during development.

Ethics and Professional Standards

I upheld strong ethical standards during my OJT, prioritizing user-centric design principles and addressing accessibility and privacy concerns. I focused on simplifying lengthy privacy policies, ensuring inclusivity, and adhering to global standards like WCAG. Furthermore, I maintained professionalism by balancing innovative features with functional usability and ensuring designs aligned with both user and organizational needs without compromising ethical standards.

IX. RECOMMENDATIONS

Advice for Future OJT Participants

As a multimedia intern, particularly a UI/UX intern, one must research and be familiarized with essential multimedia tools like WebFlow, PHP, or other relevant platforms before starting their OJT. It is necessary to have some knowledge of multimedia technologies used in the creative field for them to be efficient and effective as part of the team and will be able to give insights on project deliverables knowing the functionality and limitations of each multimedia tool.

They must also stay adaptable by expecting challenges, such as tool limitations or unexpected design issues, and approach them with an open mind and problem-solving attitude. This includes having regular communication with supervisors and team members to seek feedback and ensure alignment with project goals instead of proceeding without addressing certain issues or receiving approval from the team members.

As part of the journey, OJT trainees should embrace trends by staying updated on multimedia trends like interactive design and responsive frameworks to remain competitive in the field. However, while allowing time for experimentation and learning, they must still prioritize time management by efficiently balancing exploration and execution to meet deadlines.

Feedback on the OJT Program

Based on the trainee's experiences, the OJT Program could be improved based on the following recommendations:

- Providing a clear and structured onboarding process with tutorials or resources for commonly used tools and frameworks. This will prepare OJT participants on what multimedia technologies will they be using during the program beforehand, giving them time to familiarize themselves with these tools.
- Introducing periodic discussions with supervisors to identify strengths, areas for improvement, and skill gaps. This could help the trainees have a better understanding of their skills and work on their weaknesses earlier during the OJT.
- Offering opportunities to work on various types of projects, such as websites, apps, or multimedia campaigns, will broaden the trainee's experience. Constant exposure to real-world projects will help them familiarize themselves with the work ethics, methods, and standards used in the industry and demonstrate their skills, giving them confidence in their chosen career.

School/Institution Suggestions

The academic program could better prepare students for multimedia OJT roles by incorporating real-world project-based learning where students work on multimedia design tasks similar to industry expectations, such as creating websites, apps, or branding materials on multimedia courses. These experiences allow students to apply the theoretical knowledge of multimedia to practice. This can help students build resilience and adaptability to problems related to multimedia as they go through the workflow methodologies of the design process. Additionally, working on these projects can help students build a strong portfolio necessary for the internship application process.

In line with that, the university must also introduce new trends in multimedia technologies, techniques, and other industry-standard platforms into the curriculum such as Adobe Creative Suite (Photoshop, Illustrator, XD), Figma, Sketch, or After Effects. Regularly revising the curriculum is also suggested. Aside from revisions in the courses, the university can also offer workshops on newer technologies, including prototyping tools, video editing software, and AR/VR platforms. With this, students will become familiar with cutting-edge software ensuring they are job-ready from the start of their OJT program.

For soft skills development, the university must emphasize teamwork, adaptability, and effective communication skills through group projects or role-play scenarios. Integrating collaborative projects across disciplines, such as working with marketing or business students, and organizing mock presentations and critique

sessions to practice articulating design decisions could help students communicate clearly and effectively with team members, stakeholders, and clients when they start working on real-world projects.

Moreover, although many students already have jobs related to multimedia, the university should still offer internship opportunities for those who have not yet been exposed to the creative industry but are interested in working alongside professionals. It provides a chance to learn workplace ethics, build confidence, develop globally competitive skills, and open up career opportunities. In addition, internships give the university an opportunity to evaluate the relevance and up-to-dateness of its curriculum based on students' deliverables during the OJT program, enabling curriculum revisions as needed.

X. CONCLUSION

Overall Experience Summary

The OJT experience provided valuable insights that bridged academic learning with real-world application, offering a comprehensive understanding of multimedia technologies, design principles, and professional workflows. Working on real projects enabled me to gain a deeper understanding of technical proficiency in tools like Figma for prototyping, WebFlow for web development, and Visual Studio Code for coding HTML, CSS, and Javascript. These tools were crucial in designing responsive and user-friendly interfaces that adhered to global accessibility standards, such as WCAG.

Additionally, I was introduced to emerging trends like AI-powered tools for coding efficiently and dynamic CMS platforms, which streamlined workflows and improved project outcomes. With the guidance of the supervisor and feedback from the team, I gained hands-on experience in creating functional and visually engaging designs, ensuring they were adaptable across various devices. The experiences aided me in having a solid grasp of user-centric design, balancing creativity with practicality to meet both client and user needs. It also exposed me to the methodologies, processes and protocols used by most multimedia industries, particularly in website development.

The experience fostered personal growth by improving adaptability, teamwork, and problem-solving skills. Collaborative tasks and regular feedback sessions enhanced my ability to communicate effectively and refine designs iteratively.

Overall, the OJT experience not only equipped me with practical skills and technical expertise but also instilled a professional mindset essential for thriving in the multimedia industry.

Career Preparedness

The OJT program thoroughly prepared me for a future career in multimedia by providing hands-on experience in designing and developing user-centered interfaces. I gained technical expertise in industry tools and standards, such as WCAG for accessibility and dynamic CMS systems, which honed my adaptability to fast-paced environments. Collaborative projects enhanced my ability to work effectively in teams, while iterative feedback and rigorous testing processes improved my capacity to produce functional, visually appealing designs. Overcoming challenges like technical limitations and balancing innovation with usability strengthened my problem-solving skills, preparing me to contribute meaningfully in professional multimedia roles.

The OJT allowed me to assess my strengths and weaknesses, offering valuable opportunities for growth and improvement throughout the program. It contributed to building a strong portfolio of real-world projects that increased my potential and showcased my abilities to future employers. The experience helped establish connections and expanded my professional network, laying a solid foundation for a future career in the multimedia field. It also opened the possibility of being hired as a freelancer and absorbed by the company after the program. Through these experiences, it ensured that I am well-prepared to navigate the challenges and opportunities in the multimedia industry.

XI. APPENDICES

Appendix A: Daily Journal /Log Sheets

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 1

Intern's Name	: Laryze C. Lozano	First week "From Date"	: August 19, 2024
Company	: Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc.	Second week "To Date"	: August 30, 2024
Dept. Deployed	: Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions	Hours worked these weeks:	: 64 hours
Supervisor's Name:	: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano	Total hours completed	: 64 hours
Work Schedule	: Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)		

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 08/19/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> First synchronous online meeting with UAS Design team for the UAS website. I was assigned to do the wireframe for the website based on the sitemap they will send thru email. Phase 1 will be the wireframe for the About, Careers, and Contact page. They discussed the requirements for the website. 	1	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OJT Formalization and rendering 	5	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setting up my Figma account 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reviewing the sitemap and the color branding 	1	100
Date: 08/20/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma (<i>About us page</i>) 	3	20
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For additional work experience, I joined the meeting with the executives of Ospital ng Makati for their other project. 	5	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 08/21/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma (About us and contact us page) 	4	60
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: High-fidelity prototyping in Figma 	4	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 08/22/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma -initial layout for about us, contact us, and careers page Phase 1: High-fidelity prototyping in Figma 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Date: 08/21/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Redesigning of the "Explore opportunities" section with the guidance of my supervisor. Sending the shareable link of Figma wireframe to the design team thru Viber group chat for feedback and 	2	100

	suggestions on design and functionality.		
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sending the shareable link of Figma wireframe to the design team thru Viber group chat for feedback and suggestions on design and functionality. 	0.5	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reading comments and suggestions by the design team leader regarding the UI of the page on Figma <ol style="list-style-type: none"> About Us- Milestone section Career- Job opportunity section Career- Gallery section 	0.5	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Redesigning the milestone section 	1	20
Date: 08/23/2024	Holiday		
Time In: N/A			
Time Out: N/A			
Hours Worked: N/A			
Date: 08/26/2024	Holiday		
Time In: N/A			
Time Out: N/A			
Hours Worked: N/A			
Date: 08/27/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Redesigning the milestone section. Per brand awards instead of years. 	7	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adding department and location filter in the job opportunity section. 	1	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 08/28/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adding pagination and boxes in the gallery section. 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reviewing the contents, checking that the prototype pages and buttons work as I intended and adding details I missed. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Second synchronous online meeting with the team. I presented the wireframe/prototype I made, and they gave feedback and presented design concepts for the website. I was tasked to proceed with the UI, which incorporate the brand colors, icons, and images. After this I will be proceeding to the phase 2 of wireframing another batch of pages on the website. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Adding search bar in the job opportunity section. 	0.5	100
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exporting the 3 pages in JPEG format and sending it to the team thru Viber. 	0.5	100
Date: 08/29/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI designing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - incorporating brand yellow, white and gray brand 	8	30

	colors and design.		
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 08/30/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI designing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - incorporating brand yellow, white and gray brand colors and design. 	8	60
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			

Visual Documentation

Project Deliverable/s	Description
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Initial wireframe and prototype of About, Contact, and Careers page.

Ideation and re-designing process of Milestone section.

Phase 1 – Website Admin
 Final wireframe as approved by the team. Changes such as the milestone section, pagination in the gallery section, and filter and search bar in the job opportunity section.

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 09/02/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 09/02/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 2

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : September 2, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : September 13, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 80 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 144 hours
Work Schedule : **Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)**

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 09/02/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI designing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - incorporating the brand colors and design in the About page. - Design concept 1 	7	80
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rechecking the wireframe and assets that I need Messaging Ms. Nadine to request for the assets 	1	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/03/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI designing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finishing the design in phase 1. - Design concept 2 - Possible interactions 	8	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/04/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial layout for <i>Home</i>, <i>Solutions</i>, and <i>Insights</i> page 	6	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussing the Milestone section design with the front-end developer, Sir Joshua. 	2	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/05/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permitted Leave 		
Time In: 9:00 AM Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hs			
Date: 08/06/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Layout concept 1 for <i>Home</i> page 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Layout concepts for <i>Solution/services</i> page 	3	60
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: High-fidelity prototyping in Figma 	1	100

Hours Worked: 8 hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussing the Culture section design with the front-end developer, Sir Joshua. 	1	100
Date: 09/09/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma - Finalizing the layout for <i>Solutions</i> page 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma - Layout concepts for <i>Insights</i> page - Finalizing the layout for <i>Insights</i> page 	2	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: UI designing in Figma - Initial concepts for <i>Home</i> page 	2	40
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/10/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: UI designing in Figma - Design concept for <i>Our Commitment</i> section 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Footer layout and design. (dark and light version) 	2	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: UI designing in Figma - Layout concepts for the pages of each solution's details. 	3	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/11/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma - Reviewing the contents, checking that the prototype pages and buttons work as I intended and adding details I missed. - Sending the shareable link to Sir Joshua for checking 	2	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development: Designing and adding details on the contact page in WebFlow. 	5	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learned about UI components and interactive elements in Flowbite CSS with the guidance of Sir Joshua. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/12/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial designs for website background 	4	50
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Footer background 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edited the button design in WebFflow 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/13/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permitted Leave 		
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			

Visual Documentation		
Project Deliverable/s		Description
<p>The wireframe shows a home page layout with a top navigation bar, a hero section with a placeholder image, a 'Our Commitment' diagram with 'People', 'Process', and 'Support' nodes, a 'Our Solutions' grid of six service cards, a 'Case Studies' section with a placeholder, a 'Partners' row of placeholder boxes, an 'Insights' section with 'Articles' and 'Events' columns, a 'Work At UAS' section, and a 'Contact Us' section at the bottom. A footer contains 'MAIN PAGES', 'PAGES', and 'CONTACT' links.</p>	<p>The wireframe shows a solutions page layout with a top navigation bar, a 'Solutions' header, a grid of six service cards (Hardware and Network Equipment and Solutions, Data Center and Backup Services, Software Solutions, Hardware and Network Equipment and Solutions, Consultation Services, Contact Center Services), a 'Subscription Based Model' card, a 'Case Studies' section with a placeholder, and a footer with 'MAIN PAGES', 'PAGES', and 'CONTACT' links.</p>	<p>Phase 2 Initial wireframe and prototype of Home, Services/Solutions, and Insights page.</p>

Layout concepts for the pages of each solution's details.

Contact page made in WebFlow.

Ideation and design process of Our Commitment section.

MAIN PAGES
Home
Solutions
Insights
About UAS
Careers

PAGES
Lorem
ipsum
Consequuntur
Qui ratione

CONTACT
+63 2 8 898 8330
customercare@uas.com.ph

Email Address

@2024 [Terms of service](#) [Privacy Policy](#)

Concepts and background design for footer.

uas Home About Careers Pricing Blog Contact Us Cart

Welcome to UAS

Your trusted partner in innovative IT solutions. We are dedicated to delivering...

Mission

Vision

We are enabled committed to shape our communities through agile and evolving solutions that provide profitable and cost-efficient platforms for the future of our people. All organizations have access to success-driving technology through our self-oriented services.

Go to Settings to act

About page made in WebFlow

Our Solutions

UAS is dedicated to providing a streamlined and efficient process, ensuring solutions are delivered effectively. We value our team, emphasizing collaboration, growth, and innovation to drive success and deliver exceptional service. Our flexible payment options make our solutions accessible to all clients.

Data Center and Back-up Services

Secure and reliable data storage solutions.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

Software Solutions

Customized software to enhance productivity and efficiency.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

In-country Cloud Offerings

Tailored cloud services for optimal performance and compliance.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

Consultation

Expert advice to optimize IT infrastructure and operations.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

Contact Center Services

Comprehensive customer support solutions.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

Balance

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet consectetur. Molestie lorem arcu.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

[View All Solutions](#)

Milestones

Your trusted partner in innovative IT solutions. We are dedicated to delivering excellence through our comprehensive range of services, designed to meet the unique needs of businesses across various industries.

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

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01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

01 02 03 04 05 06 07 08 09 10 11 12

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Reach out to us for any inquiries, support, or partnership opportunities. We are here to help you achieve your goals.

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uas

Aliquam et tellus urna. Phasellus eget adipiscing elit. Mauris id nunc odio. Aliquam et tellus urna.

MAIN PAGES

Home
Solutions
Insights
About UAS

PAGES

Twitter
LinkedIn
Facebook
Instagram

CONTACT

+63 2 8 991 8330
it.customer@uas.com.ph

Careers page in WebFlow.

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 09/17/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 09/17/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 3

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : September 16, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : September 27, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 80 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 224 hours
Work Schedule : **Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)**

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 09/16/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial design for website background 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussion on the responsiveness and design of Milestone and Our Commitment section. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learned about grid, flex, and block, and position sticky in CSS 	1.5	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Listed the assets needed for phase 1 	.5	50
Date: 09/17/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Listed the assets needed for phase 1 	.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checked the phase 1 pages in WebFlow and edited details. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting for UAS website privacy policy. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: UI designing in Figma - Added details and changes in the layout 	3.5	100
Date: 09/18/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Message Ms. Nadine to request the assets needed for phase 1. 	.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development: - Made changes in the WebFlow as requested by Ms. Nadine 	4	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Created layout for phone screen version of Job Opportunity section on Career page in Figma. 	3.5	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/19/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Permitted leave 		
Time In: 9:00 AM Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 08/20/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Wireframing in Figma - Layout concept for Case Studies section on Solutions page per Ms. Nadine's request. 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Created layout design for Terms and Conditions page in Figma. 	2	100

Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Designing and adding details on Insights page. 	3	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs			
Date: 09/23/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Designing and adding details on Terms and Conditions page. 	7	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussed with Ms. Nadine the changes and additional sections to include in Phase 1. 	1	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/24/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI designing n Figma - Adding and designing the Certification section on About Page 	3	30
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Designing and adding details on Solutions page. 	4	40
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Submitted my information and answered the form from Sir Kevin as part of my OJT formalization. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/25/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Designing and adding details on Solutions page. 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development: - Embedding the code in Our commitment section 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI designing in Figma - Adding and designing the Certification section on About Page 	2	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/26/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development in CodePen - Coding and styling the Certification section using HTML and CSS 	5	50
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learned about JavaScript and reviewed the CSS properties. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 09/27/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development in CodePen - Incorporating JS in Certification section and embedding it on About page section. 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting for Makati Health Department (MHD) - Health Center Virtual Queuing Management System (QMS) Project. The agenda of the meeting was the resources, progress updates and timeline for each phase. 	1	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting in person with Ms. Nadine for her to check the development of Phase 1 in WebFlow. 	2	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confirmation of Completion: Phase 1 – Website Admin Revamp 	1	100

Visual Documentation	
Project Deliverable/s	Description
	<p>Phase 1 Small/Phone screen layout of the Milestones and Job opportunity section.</p>
	<p>Phase 2 Initial layout for Case Studies section in Figma</p>
	<p>Phase 2 Insights page in made in WebFlow</p>

Phase 2
Solutions page in made WebFlow

Phase 1
Careers section on About page in WebFlow.

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 10/01/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 10/01/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 4

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : September 30, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : October 11, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 80 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 304 hours
Work Schedule : **Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)**

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 09/30/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Read and signed the contract for the MHD project. 	1.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Messed Ms. Nadine for the new URL of the website 	.5	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing the bi-weekly report 	4	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checked the website's responsiveness 	2	100
Date: 10/01/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minimal changes in the About page as per Ms. Nadine's request. 	1	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development in WebFlow - Imported and placed the digital image badges accordingly in the Certification section on the About page in WebFlow. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI design in Figma - Modified the Home page as suggested by Sir Joshua by adding "view all" button below the article and events section 	2	50
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learned Bootstrap and its Documentation 	2	100
Date: 10/02/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: UI design in Figma and front-end development in WebFlow - Modified the Home page as suggested by Sir Joshua by adding "view all" button below the article and events section 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UI design in Figma - designed the email form submission template generated by submitting the form response in the Contact Us page 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI design in Figma - Minimal changes in Opportunity section. 	2	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/03/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development in WebFlow -Edited headings and texts in the website for consistency 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installed and set up software tools needed for web development. 	4	80

Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/04/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting for UAS website privacy policy. 	1	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Received the company-issued laptop. Installed and set up software tools needed. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development in WebFlow - Added link to social media icons in the footer. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting for Makati Health Department (MHD) - Health Center Virtual Queuing Management System (QMS) Project. The agenda of the meeting was the progress updates and phase 1 timeline. 	1	100
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Edited articles and events dynamic page template. 	2	100
Date: 10/07/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Created CMS for each solution and designed the dynamic page template. 	8	80
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/08/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Created CMS for each solution and designed the dynamic page template. - Added details in CMS for each solution 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development in WebFlow - Added background on other pages. 	1	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Edited collapsible index sidebar on the Terms and Conditions page for smaller screens.	3	40
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/09/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Edited the Solutions' dynamic page's responsiveness on smaller devices. - Modified the design. 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learned back-end and front end. 	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installed Composer and Laravel. Set up software and the environment needed for the MHD project. 	2	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/10/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Edited collapsible index sidebar on Terms and Conditions page for smaller screens. 	7	80
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Proposed a schedule to set the mid-OJT meeting. 	1	100
Date: 10/11/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 2: Front-end development in WebFlow - Edited collapsible index sidebar on Terms and Conditions page for smaller screens. 	7	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting with MHD. The agenda 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs	of the meeting was the deployment of the QMS website to the server and internal and external meetings.		

Visual Documentation		
Project Deliverable/s		Description
		<p>Phase 2 Dynamic page template of each solution page and its responsiveness on smaller screens.</p>
		<p>Responsiveness and sidebar index of Terms and Conditions page.</p>

<p>Insights Articles and events featuring graphics, photos, videos, and developments.</p> <p>Articles</p> <p>Events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> September 25, 2024 Summer Music Festival 2023 A three-day music festival featuring local and national artists, food, and fun for everyone. September 25, 2024 Tech Conference 2023 A premier event for all technology enthusiasts, featuring speakers and networking opportunities. September 25, 2024 Health Fair 2023 A community event focused on health and wellness with free screenings and workshops. September 25, 2024 Annual Art Exhibition 2023 A showcase of local artists, with an opening reception and activities. 	<p>Phase 2 Insights section on Home page.</p>
<p>You just got a form submission! Contact Us Submission Form</p> <p>Name: Lorem Ipsum Email: lorem@ipsum@gmail.com Mobile Number: 09492123456 Company: Company Industry: Industry Subject: Subject Message: Message</p> <p>Go to site Review submissions</p> <p><small>If you believe this is a spam submission, please forward to form-spam-report@bluewin.ch © 2024 Universal Access Systems and Solutions. All rights reserved.</small></p>	<p>Contact form submission template sent to email.</p>

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 10/15/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 10/15/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 5

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : October 14, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : October 25, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 80 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 384 hours
Work Schedule : Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 09/14/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code - Styled the modal for privacy policy on Login page 	2.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Styled the appointments table	2	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Styled the registration form	1.5	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learned about Bootstrap and VS code 	2	100
Date: 10/15/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code (Master Admin) - Styled the Personnel page 	2	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Styled the Facilities page	2	70
Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Styled the Schedule page	2	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs	- Styled the List of Services page	2	80
Date: 10/16/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code (Patient Admin) - Styled the Edit Profile page 	3	70
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Styled the Password page	2	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Styled the Dependents page	3	80
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/17/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code (Health Personnel) - Styled the Daily Appointments page 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Styled the Weekly Appointments page	3	80
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code (Master Admin) - Styled the Appointments page 	2	100
Date: 10/18/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for UAS Website in WebFlow - Created CMS for Employee Highlights section on About page 	3	100

Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documenting User Story for UAS website <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solutions page Insights page Instance and templates 	4	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting with MHD- QMS. The agenda of the meeting was the updates regarding phase 1. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs			
Date: 10/21/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code (Master Admin) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Completed the styling of each page 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Back-end development for UAS website <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emailing system for contact form submission using third party applications. 	5	60
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/22/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code (Patient and Health Personnel) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Completed the styling of each page 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Back-end development for UAS website <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emailing system for contact form submission using third party applications. 	4	70
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/23/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Back-end development for UAS website <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emailing system for contact form submission and newsletter using third party applications. 	7.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mid-OJT meeting with Prof. Luisa and Sir Joshua. Discussed the development of the project, my performance, and the final report. 	0.5	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/24/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Completed and reviewed the styling of each page 	8	60
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/25/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: UI design for UAS Website in Figma <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layout and design for Job opportunity details page 	3	50
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Completed and reviewed the styling of each page 	5	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs			

Visual Documentation	
Project Deliverable/s	Description
<p>Figure 1. Job Details page template</p>	<p>Phase 1 - UAS Website Design for the dynamic page template for job opportunity details page.</p>
<p>Figure 2. Job Details page template</p>	<p>Phase 1 - MHD-QMS Login page with modal containing the privacy policy.</p>
<p>Figure 3.1. Personnel page</p>	<p>Phase 1 - MHD-QMS Master Admin Account</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personnel - Facilities - Schedule - List of Services - Appointments - Announcements

Figure 3.2. Facilities page

Figure 3.3. Schedule page

Figure 3.4. List of Services page

Figure 3.5. Appointments page

Figure 3.6. Announcements page

Figure 4.1. Daily Appointments page

Figure 4.2. Weekly Appointments page

Phase 1 - MHD-QMS
 Health Personnel
 Account
 - Daily Appointment
 - Weekly Appointments

Figure 5.1. Edit Profile page

Phase 1 - MHD-QMS
 Patient Account
 - Edit Profile
 - Password
 - Appointments
 - Dependents

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 10/31/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 10/31/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 6

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : October 28, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : November 8, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 73 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 457 hours
Work Schedule : Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 10/28/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UI design for UAS Website in Figma - Layout and design for Job opportunity details page 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Styled the Job opportunity details page 	5	80
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/29/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Styled the Job opportunity details page 	5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Fixed the responsiveness and added trigger animation	3	40
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/30/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Fixed the responsiveness and added trigger animation 	8	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 10/31/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Fixed the rotate-on-hover animation in Employee Highlights section 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	Half-day at work	5	
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/01/2024	Holiday		
Time In: 9:00 AM			

Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: N/A			
Date: 11/04/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code - Fixed responsiveness for heading and logo 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Fixed responsiveness for Master Admin account page	4	80
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/05/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase 1: Front-end development for MHD-QMS in Visual Studio Code - Fixed responsiveness for Master Admin account page 	2	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Fixed responsiveness for Health Validator account page	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Fixed responsiveness for Patient account page	3	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/06/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UI design for UAS Website in Figma - Layout and design for Case Study page 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Styled the Case Study page 	5	70
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/07/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Styled the Case Study page 	2	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	- Edited the content of Case Study pages	6	50
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/08/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Front-end development for UAS Website in Webflow - Edited the content of Case Study pages 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM	- Reviewed the content of Case Study pages and the links	3	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synchronous online meeting with MHD. The agenda of the meeting was the development of the QMS website and timeline. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs			

Visual Documentation

Project Deliverable/s **Description**

Figure 1. Job offers page template

Dynamic page template for job opportunity details page.

Figure 2. Case Studies section

Case Studies section in Solutions page.

Case Study page template design in laptop, tablet and mobile screens

Figure 3.1. Case Study page in laptop screens

Figure 3.2. Case Study page in tablet screens

Figure 3.3. Case Study page in mobile screens

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 11/12/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 11/12/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 7

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : November 11, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : November 22, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 80 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 536 hours
Work Schedule : **Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)**

DATE / TIME	Task			
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed	
Date: 11/11/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100	
Time In: 9:00 AM			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing my OJT bi-weekly report. 	30
Time Out: 6:00 PM Hours Worked: 8hrs				
Date: 11/12/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100	
Time In: 9:00 AM			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing my OJT bi-weekly report. 	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM Hours Worked: 8hrs				
Date: 11/13/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100	
Time In: 9:00 AM			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emailed the OJT bi-weekly report to Ma'am Luisa. 	100
Time Out: 6:00 PM Hours Worked: 8hrs				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Started writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project.
Date: 11/14/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100	
Time In: 9:00 AM			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Started writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	15
Time Out: 6:00 PM Hours Worked: 8hrs				
Date: 11/15/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100	
Time In: 9:00 AM			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Started writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	20
Time Out: 6:00 PM Hours Worked: 8hrs				
Date: 11/18/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100	
Time In: 9:00 AM				

Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Started writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 		25
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/19/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	8	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Started writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 		30
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/20/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	6.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discussing the final requirements for completing my OJT period with Sir Kevin, head of talent Acquisition, including obtaining my certificate and sealing the evaluation form that will be provided by my supervisor. 	1	100
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/21/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Started writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	5	35
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 11/22/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setting up my UAS email account on Outlook and requesting access for Workforce Tracker app. 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> QA Testing of UAS Website 	3	37
Hours Worked: 8 hrs			
Date: 11/22/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessing the layout and design of the current workforce app. 	3	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Company Event from 4pm-6pm 	2	100
Hours Worked: 8 hrs			

Visual Documentation

Project Deliverable/s **Description**

DOCUMENT TITLE:

Customer:	UAS
Title:	User Acceptance Test
Document Name:	UAS User Acceptance Test – Company Website Tracker

ACCEPTANCE REQUIREMENT	TEST RESULT		COMMENTS
	ACCEPT	REJECT	
1. Home Page			
General Access			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Should be able to see header and UAS Video. Embed Video is playing, and initially muted. Our Commitment section is visible and animating with revolution. Hovering on the axis will make the revolution faster Hovering on any of the 4 commitment capsules (People, Process, etc.) will show its description directly below it. Our Solutions section is visible, shows a total of 6 solutions and a button "View All Solutions" to direct a viewer to the Solutions page. By clicking "View All Solutions" button directs you to the Solutions page. Every solution shown below should have a button on each of them and directs you to their perspective page. Partners section is visible and traversing from right to left. Insights section is visible, showing two sections "Articles" and "Events" Articles section shows only an image. Hovering on any article will show its description inside, sliding from below. Events section shows an image and its description below (Date, title, and description). Hovering on any events will move the image and description upwards Clicking on any of the articles will direct you to its perspective subpage. Clicking on any of the events will direct you to its perspective subpage. 			

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2

UAS Company Website User Acceptance Test form.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "View All Articles" button is visible and directs you to the insights page with the tab initially on articles section 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "View All Events" button is visible and directs you to the insights page with the tab initially on events section 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work at UAS Section is visible, containing the title, a description, a button, and an image beside it. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By pressing the "Join Us" button you will be directed to the Contact Us page. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach out to us section is visible. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By pressing the "Contact Us" button you will be directed to the Contact Us page. 			
2. Solutions Page			
General Access			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions section is visible, shows a total of 7 solutions. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every solution shown below should have a button on each of them and directs you to their perspective page. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case studies section is visible, shows a total of 9 case studies. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every case study shown below should have a button on each of them and directs you to their perspective page. 			
2.1 Solutions Sub Page			
General Access			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should show the title, its description, and a corresponding image of the clicked solution on the top-most yellow section of the page. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should show all the icons, characteristics and description on each column section on the white section of the page. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk to Us section is visible 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By pressing "Talk to Us!" button, it will direct you to the Contact Us page. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Solutions" or "View More/All Solutions" section is visible showing only 3 solutions and a "View all Solutions" button. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By clicking "View All Solutions" button directs you to the Solutions page. 			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Every solution shown below should have a button on each of them and directs you to their perspective page. 			

 108-109 Reliance IT Center Building, 99 E. Rodriguez Jr. Ave., Pasig City Metro Manila, Philippines
 www.uas.com.ph
 customer@uas.com.ph

INTERNSHIP EVALUATION FORM

Intern's Name :	Larysa C. Lozano	Internship Start Date :	August 19, 2024
Company :	Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc.	Internship End Date :	December 4, 2024
Dept. Deployed :	Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions	Completion of Form Date :	November 20, 2024
Supervisor's Name :	Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano	Total Training Hours :	600 Hours
Work Schedule :	Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)		

SUMMARY

BUSINESS STRATEGY	WEIGHT	FINAL RATING	OVERALL SCORE
KNOWLEDGE AND APPLICATION OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES	35%	35.00%	100.00%
UI/UX DESIGN SKILLS AND APPLICATION	35%	35.00%	
COMPETENCIES IN PROJECT CONTRIBUTION AND COLLABORATION	30%	30.00%	
TOTAL	100%		

MMS 200 Terminal Evaluation

Knowledge and Application of Multimedia Technologies

During the internship/CUT placement, to what extent did the student demonstrate the competencies which the BAMS program aims to develop in students?

Objective	Target	Weight	Rating	Remarks
Demonstrate understanding of various multimedia information and communication technologies	Successfully integrate and utilize at least three different multimedia technologies in projects, with no major issues reported.	25%	5	Exemplary integration of multiple multimedia technologies, successfully utilizing a combination of tools and platforms with no major issues reported. Demonstrates a strong understanding of how these technologies interconnect to achieve project goals.
Applies current multimedia trends and best practices in their work	Incorporate at least three current multimedia trends or best practices into projects, as evaluated by peer or supervisor reviews.	25%	5	Consistently incorporates the latest multimedia trends and adheres to industry best practices. Peers and supervisors regularly commended the work for being both innovative and effective in applying these trends.
Understand the principles of UI/UX design and their application.	Apply UI/UX principles effectively in 90% of design projects, with positive feedback from users and stakeholders.	25%	5	Exhibits a deep understanding of UI/UX principles, applying them effectively in design projects with consistently positive feedback from users and stakeholders. Demonstrates a keen eye for user-centered design.
Show creativity and innovation in multimedia solutions and content creation.	Present innovative solutions or content in at least two major projects or assignments, with recognition from peers or supervisors for creativity.	25%	5	Has created responsive code ideas in two major projects (MVC and UML Notepad) and presented innovative strategies for user experience. Modern design and animation solutions are also included in this matter.
Total Grade		100%	35% / 35%	

UI/UX Design Skills and Application

During the internship/CUT placement, to what extent did the student demonstrate the competencies which the BAMS program aims to develop in UI/UX design?

Objective	Target	Weight	Rating	Remarks
Creates user-friendly and visually appealing interface designs.	Achieve a user satisfaction rating of 85% or higher on design feedback.	30%	5	Fast and flexible, the layout made in both website and prototype are aligned with the branding of the company and its theme are.
Develops effective prototypes that clearly communicate design concepts	Complete 90% of prototypes with no major revisions required during stakeholder review.	25%	5	User feedback and experience is prioritized in the design of the digital prototype designs, there has no revisions but change request for additional features has been initiated upon review.
Shows proficiency in relevant software (e.g., Figma, WordPress, WebFlow).	Demonstrate advanced skills in at least two of the listed tools, with no significant issues identified in related systems.	30%	5	Skilled in Figma and Webflow in solutions, exactly how the client wants it to be presented both in prototype and website.
Shows proficiency in HTML and CSS and delivers proper coding standards.	Maintain a code quality score of 75% or higher in code reviews, following best practices and coding standards.	15%	5	Code structure and quality in CSS and HTML shows confidence and techniques from scratch, writing, up to browser, Adaptive and flexible in most solutions.
Total Grade		100%	35% / 35%	

Competencies in Project Contribution and Collaboration

During the internship/CUT placement, to what extent did the student apply skills which a senior undergraduate student from any discipline is expected to possess?

Objective	Target	Weight	Rating	Remarks
Contributes fresh perspectives and innovative ideas	Present at least four new ideas or perspectives in each major project, with at least one idea implemented or acknowledged as valuable.	25%	5	Prototype and solutions are ingenious and modern, these enabled more options for work around in case of conflicts. She brainstormed with the team to plan out the website process & alternative designs.
Incorporates their supervisor's feedback to enhance the quality of their work and/or improve their workflow.	Act on 100% of actionable feedback received from supervisors, demonstrating improvement in work quality or workflow efficiency in subsequent projects.	25%	5	Supervisor's suggestions and feedback are effective upon discussion. This made the workflow optimal and has been evident since project startup. Revisions was done ahead of time.
Collaborates effectively with the project team that communicates ideas and concepts clearly	Achieve a team collaboration rating of 85% or higher in peer reviews, with clear and effective communication noted in project evaluations.	25%	5	Communication towards other team members are clear and considerate. Ideas and concepts are discussed in an established manner, leading to smoother execution on implementation.
Delivers work that meets or exceeds project requirements within given deadlines.	100% completion of UI/UX tasks within the allocated days	25%	5	Large in every aspect to work with and deliver respect to her team. Tasks and deliverables are completed ahead of the set deadlines, giving the team extra time to address unexpected errors, make improvements, and implement changes as needed.
Total Grade		100%	35% / 35%	

RATING GUIDE

PERFORMANCE RATING	RATING DESCRIPTION
5 - OUTSTANDING PERFORMANCE	Exceptional results. Successfully achieves all established goals and objectives and significantly exceeds expectations for quality, impact on the business, and/or turnaround time. Capabilities far exceed the knowledge and skills required in the field.
4 - EXCEEDS EXPECTATION	Successfully achieves all established goals and objectives and significantly exceeds expectations for quality, impact on the business, and/or turnaround time. Capabilities far exceed the knowledge and skills required in the job.
3 - SOLID PERFORMANCE	Meets expectations. Solid value-added performance. Demonstrates the knowledge, skills and behaviors required in the job. Effectively and efficiently handles assigned duties and responsibilities. Successfully achieves goals and objectives.
2 - IMPROVEMENT REQUIRED	Below expectations. Meets some but not all expectations on the job.
1 - UNSATISFACTORY PERFORMANCE	Consistently fails to meet job requirements.

Intern's Details

Larysa C. Lozano
Student's Name
(signature above printed name)

Prepared and Evaluated by:

Joshua Rene Mariano
Internship Supervisor
(signature above printed name)

Nadine Faye Alarcon
Creatives Head & Coordinator
(signature above printed name)

Received by:

Asst. Professor Luriza Orellana
MMS 200 Advisor for Larysa Lozano
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Emely Amolico
UPOU-FICS BAMS Program Chair
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Diego Maranan
Dean, UP Open University Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, BAMS MMS 200 Coordinator
(signature above printed name)

Internship Evaluation Form with grade and remarks from my OJT evaluators.

<p style="text-align: center;">ON-THE-JOB TRAINING REPORT</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Laryze C. Lozano</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Universal Access And Systems Solutions Philippines Inc.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">August 19, 2024 To December __, 2024</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Submitted On:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">December __, 2024</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">1. Introduction</p> <p>Purpose of the Report</p> <p>The purpose of documenting On-the-Job training experience is to reflect the practical application of the theoretical knowledge on multimedia learned in the academic setting. This report records the company's background, OJT description, weekly tasks, challenges, contributions, and accomplishments in the company. It also includes the trainee's multimedia use, technique, and soft and technical skills gained during the internship. This documentation helps to evaluate the learning outcomes and provides insight for future professional and personal development.</p> <p>Objectives of the OJT</p> <p>The objective of the OJT includes the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To demonstrate and apply the theoretical knowledge and technical skills acquired in multimedia from academic settings to the professional field. 2. To gain hands-on experience by working on real-world projects and develop professional competencies such as communication, teamwork, and problem-solving skills in the work settings. 3. To explore new and emerging multimedia technologies and trends, including such as responsive design, accessibility standards, and user-centric methodologies. 	<p style="text-align: center;">Draft of the Final Report for MMS 200 in-progress.</p>
<p>Significance of OJT in Career Development</p> <p>The On-the-Job training is crucial for the development of multimedia students' skills, design thinking, and competencies relevant to the professional field, and bridges the gap between theory and practice. They will gain valuable experience through working on a project, collaborating with the team, and communicating with the client and stakeholders. They will also gain valuable insight into their abilities and have the opportunity to enhance their skills through feedback from industry professionals. By reflecting on their accomplishments and evaluating their tasks, they can identify areas for improvement. This process not only builds their confidence but also equips them to excel in their chosen career path.</p> <p>In the local setting, the OJT helps adapt to the region-specific user preference and cultural nuances, ensuring that the design or digital product they produce would be impactful and relevant. In the localization of a digital product, the designer or creator must understand and meet the cultural, linguistic, and behavioral preferences of the target audience to enhance user-centric design and functionality in accordance with their needs.</p> <p>In the global context, the OJT plays a significant role in introducing new multimedia technologies, such as AI technology, and emerging trends in techniques, protocols, and methods for user-centric designs to multimedia intern that is used globally. It equips them to be competitive in the global market and to also contribute to multimedia initiatives.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">2. Profile Of the Institution Where the OJT was Conducted</p> <p>Universal Access Systems and Solutions Inc. (UAS) is a forward-thinking company dedicated to empowering organizations by providing agile and evolving IT solutions that shape and support communities since 2005. With their professionals with more than 20 years of experience in information technology, they bring technological innovative solutions that bring people and technology together and help various companies thrive with new technology. Over the years, their partners have recognized them, driven by their four founding pillars: Best-of-breed IT infrastructure, enterprise solutions, pure fiber connectivity, and managed services.</p> <p>They are committed to shaping communities "through agile and evolving solutions that provide profitable and cost-efficient platforms for the future of our people" and a vision to provide "access to success-driving technology" to all organizations through their service-oriented services. Their services and products include IT infrastructure solutions, software solutions, cabling and connectivity, managed services, and industry solutions.</p> <p>The OJT trainee was supervised by Sir Joshua Rene Mendez Mariano, a Development Networks Engineer in the Bus, Innovation & Digital Solutions Department all throughout the duration of the OJT. As an OJT supervisor, he coordinated with UP Open University stakeholders on behalf of UAS Solutions Inc. and ensured a smooth process of the OJT program. Through him, the trainee was introduced to new multimedia technologies and emerging trends utilized by their company.</p>	

<p>Multimedia Technology Adoption</p> <p>UAS leverages the use of multimedia technologies and trends to deliver software solutions. Their design team uses tools like Adobe Creative Suite to create designs and other media products for promotional purposes and assets for websites and systems. As for their software developers, they use Visual Studio Code, XAMPP, GitHub, and Gitbash. They also utilize the Laravel framework, Javascript Vanilla, JQuery, PHP, and other available languages apart from HTML and CSS. When it comes to UI/UX design and front-end development, online libraries for fonts, color themes, CSS components libraries (e.g. Flawtyte, Tailwind, and Bootstrap), and icon libraries (e.g. Heroicons). For building websites or application systems, they also use various platforms such as WebFlow, WordPress, and Microsoft Power Apps that use less code and have ready-built sections and templates for websites, making the work faster and easier.</p> <p>Due to the nature of the work, they also adopted collaboration platforms for team meetings and updates such as Webex, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams and other cloud-based productivity and collaboration tools for efficiency.</p> <p>Protocols and Standard</p> <p>Upon the start of the project, they prioritize defining the company's brand design, including its color palette, font style, and design approach, ensuring brand consistency across all platforms. As much as possible, they aim for a modern and</p>	<p>intuitive design while still following the company's brand. Functionally-wise, they make sure that the multimedia project is responsive, adaptive to all screen sizes, accessible, and user-oriented, adhering to the basic standard for website and application user interface.</p> <p>After completing each phase, they ensure to document the user journey/story which serves as a manual to make it easier for the owner and user to navigate through the site or application. Once the developers have completed the pages of the site as well as its design and functionality, it must undergo Quality Assurance and be reviewed by the owner before it is officially ready for deployment. The QA tester will ensure the overall quality of the site or application, ensuring that all the project objectives and requirements have been met and there are no major issues.</p> <p>Integration of Innovative Multimedia Trends</p> <p>As an IT solutions company, they encourage their people to leverage innovative trends that can enhance the quality of their work, ensuring flexibility cost-effectiveness, and efficiency. Innovative trends like AI-powered tools, such as AI chatbots (e.g. ChatGPT), are utilized to help developers with their code. Dynamic Content Management System (CMS) feature with AI integration on a custom website builder platform with noless code, such as WebFlow, aids their developers to create, manage, and generate content more easily. Moreover, platforms like WebFlow and WordPress offer integrations and custom code support for flexibility and extending functionality for developers.</p>	
<p>3. Training Program Description</p> <p>The trainee's 600 hours of On-the-Job Training in the Bus. Innovation & Digital Solutions Department started on August 19, 2024 and ended on December 19, 2024. The Bus. Innovation & Digital Solutions Department. The OJT program required the trainee to work for a full eight hours from Monday to Friday.</p> <p>Responsibilities and Duties</p> <p>During the duration of the OJT, the main responsibilities and duties of the trainee involve the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Create UI/UX designing and prototyping for the main website on the website transfer project. This includes researching user needs, defining clear objectives, and collaborating with the stakeholders to gather requirements. The work involves creating wireframes and developing an interactive prototype in Figma while ensuring that the design is visually appealing and enhances user engagement and experience when using the website, meeting the project objectives. Learn basic HTML/CSS and have lab exercises for assessment. This involves understanding the basic structures of styling web pages, covering topics on HTML elements, attributes, and CSS properties, and 	<p>applying these concepts in practical lab exercises for assessment to gauge an understanding and proficiency in HTML/CSS.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Create improvements for the user interface on currently deployed websites and applications. It includes analyzing user feedback and performance metrics to identify areas of enhancements on currently deployed website. The process involves enhancing the user interface for better experience and engagement, improving and updating the visual design, and ensuring consistency and intuitive user experience across all devices. Learn about the Webflow platform and Laravel framework. It involves understanding their functionalities and applications. For Webflow, it involves mastering content management, CMS, and building web pages. For Laravel, it on Attend meetings for the website transfer alignment. It includes actively engaging in discussion, communication, and collaboration with the team to ensure that the project goals, timeline, and requirements are met, including clarifying designs, functionality expectations, addressing technical considerations, and coordinating tasks with the team. Daily activity reporting. It involved documenting, reporting, and summarizing tasks, progress, and achievements accomplished within a workday. 	

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 11/27/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 11/12/2024

BIWEEKLY PROGRESS REPORT No. 8

Intern's Name : Laryze C. Lozano **First week "From Date"** : November 25, 2024
Company : Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc. **Second week "To Date"** : December 4, 2024
Dept. Deployed : Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions **Hours worked these weeks:** 64 hours
Supervisor's Name: Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano **Total hours completed** : 600 hours
Work Schedule : Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)

DATE / TIME	Task		
	Description	Hours Spent	Status / % Completed
Date: 11/25/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireframing in Figma for UAS workforce tracker 	5	20
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	3	40
Date: 11/26/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UAT Testing of UAS Website 	6	40
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	2	45
Date: 11/27/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UAT Testing of UAS Website 	6	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireframing in Figma for UAS workforce tracker 	1.5	100
Date: 11/28/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting with UAS team for the workforce tracker system. 	.5	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Synchronous online meeting with Sir Chris for the workforce tracker system wireframe. 		
Date: 11/29/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layout designing in Figma for UAS workforce tracker 	5	30
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	3	50
Date: 12/02/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layout designing in Figma for UAS workforce tracker 	8	50
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs			
Date: 12/03/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layout designing in Figma for UAS workforce tracker 	6	70
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	2	55
Date: 12/04/2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Layout designing in Figma for UAS workforce tracker 	4	100
Time In: 9:00 AM			
Time Out: 6:00 PM			
Hours Worked: 8hrs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Writing the draft of the OJT Final Report for MMS 200 Special Project. 	4	60

Visual Documentation		Description
Project Deliverable/s		

UAS Workforce Tracker System UI Design in Figma (Dark version)

UAS Workforce Tracker System UI Design in Figma (Light version)

Prepared by:

Intern's Signature
Date: 12/04/2024

Mariano, Joshua Rene M.
Supervisor's Printed Name & Signature
Date: 11/12/2024

Appendix B: Photos of Projects Accomplished

A. Universal Access and System Solutions - Official Website

Figure 1.1. Home page of UAS Website

Figure 1.2. Solutions page of UAS website

Figure 1.3. About page of UAS website

Find a Career You're Passionate About

If you thrive on challenges, believe in the impact of technology and innovation, and are driven to empower yourself and others, UAS is the place for you.

Join our Team

Our Culture

Employee Highlight

See what our employees have to say about working at UAS!

Khye Muyco
Marketing Executive

Keneth Capsitano
Senior Multimedia Artist

Mariel Lagman
Marketing Executive

Lorraine Yabut
Multimedia Artist

Explore Your Opportunities

Click on the links below to view details for each job opportunity.

Department <input type="text"/> Location <input type="text"/> Search <input type="text"/>			
HR Coordinator	Human Resources	UAS Savers	We are hiring an HR Coordinator to support our human resources department.
Web Developer	Software Delivery	UAS Pasig	Seeking a Web Developer to create and maintain our website.
Financial Analyst	Finance	UAS Savers	Join us as a Financial Analyst to analyze financial data and trends.
Customer Service Representative	Customer Support	UAS Pasig	We are looking for a Customer Service Representative to assist our clients.
Software Engineer	Software Delivery	UAS Savers	We are looking for a skilled Software Engineer to join our team.

Gallery

Figure 1.4. Careers page of UAS website

Figure 1.5. Contact Us page of UAS website

B. Makati Health Department - Queuing Management System

Figure 2.1. Login page of MHD-QMS

The screenshot shows the registration page of the Makati Health Department Virtual Queuing Management System. The page has a blue header with the Makati Health Department logo and the text "MAKATI QUEUING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM". Below the header is a registration form with the following fields: "First Name:" (required), "Middle Name:", "Last Name:" (required), "Suffix:", "Email:" (required), "Password:" (required), "Confirm Password:" (required), "Birthdate:" (required, format dd/mm/yyyy), "Gender:" (required, dropdown menu with "Male" selected), "Mobile Number:" (required, format 09XXXXXXXX), "Address:" (required), "Barangay:" (required, dropdown menu with "Bangkal" selected), and "Yellow Card Number:". A "Register" button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 2.2. Registration page of MHD-QMS

The screenshot shows the password page of the Makati Health Department Virtual Queuing Management System. The page has a white background and a black border. It contains two password input fields: "New Password" and "Confirm New Password". Below each input field is a "Show Password" checkbox. At the bottom of the page is a "Change Password" button.

Figure 2.3. Password page of MHD-QMS

a. Master Administrator Dashboard

Figure 2.4.1. Personnel page

Figure 2.4.2. Facilities page

Figure 2.4.3. Schedule page

Figure 2.4.4. List of Services page

Figure 2.4.5. Master Admin Appointments page

Figure 2.4.6. Announcement page

b. Health Administrator Dashboard

Figure 2.5.1. Daily Appointments page

Figure 2.5.2. Weekly Appointments page

c. Patient Dashboard

MAKATI QUEUEING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

John A. Doe

- Book An Appointment
- Edit Profile**
- Password
- Appointments
- Dependents
- Logout

First Name *
Middle Name
Last Name *
Birthday *
Sex *
Phone Number *
Address *
 Outside Makati? Yes
Barangay*
Yellow Card Number

Figure 2.6.1. Edit Profile page

MAKATI QUEUEING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

John A. Doe

- Book An Appointment
- Edit Profile**
- Password
- Appointments**
- Dependents
- Logout

Ticket No.	Status	Date and Timeslot	Health Facility	Name	Action
	Pending	10/14/2024 8:00AM - 5:00PM	San Antonio	John A. Doe	Cancel

Showing items 1 to 1 of 1 items

Figure 2.6.2. Patient Appointments page

MAKATI QUEUEING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

John A. Doe

- Book An Appointment
- Edit Profile
- Password
- Appointments
- Dependents**
- Logout

First Name *
Middle Name
Last Name *
Birthday *
Sex *

First Name	Middle Name	Last Name	Birthdate	Sex	Action
Joe	A	Jane	07/09/2016	Female	<input type="button" value="Edit"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>

Showing items 1 to 1 of 1 items

Figure 2.6.3. Dependents page

d. QMS Application Introduced to the Public in Makati's Official Facebook Page

Figure 2.7. Facebook post of Makati QMS application by Makati Government [My Makati]

C. UAS Staff Management Tracker (STracker) UI/UX Design in Figma

a. Client Dashboard

Figure 3.1.1 Client dashboard summary page

Figure 3.1.2. Edit client page

Figure 3.1.3. Add client page

b. Employee Dashboard

Figure 3.2.1. Employee profile dashboard profile page

Figure 3.2.2. Employee 'transfer staff' modal

Figure 3.2.3. Add employee page

Figure 3.3. Menu dropdown

Appendix C: Documents/Certificates

A. Training Form

FACULTY OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION STUDIES
UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY

Maahas, Los Baños, Laguna 4031
(049) 536 6001 to 06 loc. 841, 334; 536-5993

30 July 2024

DR. MELINDA DP. BANDALARIA
Chancellor
UP Open University
Los Baños, Laguna

Dear Chancellor Bandalaria,

I am happy to inform you about an initiative being undertaken by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies (FICS) to enhance the educational experience of our Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies (BAMS) students through practical training opportunities. FICS is currently exploring the implementation of On-the-Job Training (OJT) and internships as a means to fulfill the requirements for the MMS 200 capstone projects. This approach aims to provide our students with valuable hands-on experience that complements their academic learning.

I am pleased to share that the IT company, Universal Access and Systems Solutions (UAS), has offered a paid OJT opportunity to one of our BAMS students, Laryze Lozano. This collaboration has undergone thorough vetting by our Institutional Linkages Officer, and I have attached the verification document for your reference.

Moreover, the training plan associated with this internship has been reviewed and approved by UPOU's Legal Office. They have advised us to designate you as the signatory on the training plan, which is also attached for your review.

We would like to utilize the UAS internship as a pilot program to assess the potential of OJTs and internships for MMS 200. Assistant Professor Luisa Gelisan will serve as the adviser for the MMS 200 course, ensuring proper guidance and oversight throughout the internship process.

FICS and UAS have agreed on a regular monitoring form to track the progress and performance of the student during the internship.

In light of these developments, may I kindly request your signature on the training plan to formalize this arrangement?

Thank you for your attention to this matter. I look forward to your favorable response.

Sincerely,

DR. DIEGO S. MARANAN
Dean and MMS 200 Coordinator
FICS

DR. EMELY M. AMOLOZA
BAMS Program Chair
FICS

CC: Assistant Professor Luisa Gelisan
Legal Office
Institutional Linkages

OFFICE OF THE CHANCELLOR
UP OPEN UNIVERSITY

RECEIVED
AUG 05 2024

By: _____ Ref. No.: **NO 24 1088**

APPROVED:

MELINDA DP. BANDALARIA
Chancellor

upou.edu.ph/home | fics@upou.edu.ph

**UNIVERSAL ACCESS AND SYSTEM SOLUTIONS
IT OPERATION DEPARTMENT**

On-the-Job Training (OJT) Training Plan

Part 1: Company and On-the-Job-Trainee (OJT) Information

Complete the contact information for the Employer and the Trainee.

COMPANY NAME: UNIVERSAL ACCESS AND SYSTEMS SOLUTIONS PHILIPPINES INC.		
ADDRESS: 108-109 IT RELIANCE CENTER CONVERGE BUILDING, E RODRIGUEZ PASIG CITY		
MAIN LINE OF BUSINESS: IT - SYSTEMS INTEGRATION		
TRAINEE NAME: Laryze Co Lozano	EMAIL: laryze19@gmail.com	TELEPHONE #: 09452805310
BEGINNING DATE: July 29, 2024.	ESTIMATED END DATE: November 8, 2024	TOTAL TRAINING HOURS: 600 Hours
STIPEND/ALLOWANCE (SPECIFY AMT IF APPLICABLE): ₱ 200 per completion of 8 hours	Others (e.g. free shuttle, free meal, etc.) (Optional)	

Part 2: Project Details

PROJECT TITLE: On-the-Job Training UIUX Website Transfer Collaboration Program	
PROJECT OBJECTIVES: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To provide hands-on experience and practical knowledge to a trainee in the field of UI/UX design. To support the professional development of the trainee in designing Figma, prototyping, and user interface/user experience (UI/UX) design. To identify and cultivate potential future employees for UAS. To enhance productivity and innovation within UAS through fresh perspectives and ideas. 	
BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT: The On-the-Job Training (OJT) Program at UAS focuses on offering a comprehensive learning experience to a single trainee specializing in UI/UX design. This program is designed to provide practical knowledge and hands-on experience in designing Figma, creating prototypes, and improving user interfaces and user experiences. The trainee will work closely with our experienced UI/UX design team, participating in various design projects and tasks. This program aims to equip the trainee with the skills and knowledge needed to excel in the field of UI/UX design, while also contributing fresh perspectives and innovative ideas to UAS. Through structured supervision and evaluation, we aim to ensure a valuable and enriching experience for the trainee, ultimately fostering their professional growth and potential integration into the UAS team.	
PROJECT TYPE:	
<input type="checkbox"/> SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT <input type="checkbox"/> MODULE OR COMPONENT DEVELOPMENT <input type="checkbox"/> COMPLETE SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WEBSITE (BSCS-IST) OR WEB APPLICATIONS DEVELOPMENT	<input type="checkbox"/> INFORMATION SYSTEMS SUPPORT ACTIVITIES <input type="checkbox"/> TECHNICAL WRITING <input type="checkbox"/> USER TECHNICAL SUPPORT ACTIVITIES <input type="checkbox"/> TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH <input type="checkbox"/> TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING <input type="checkbox"/> OTHERS, PLEASE SPECIFY: TECHNICAL SUPPORT

Part 3: Training Information (please use a separate sheet for part 3 if necessary)

Complete the training outline and estimated time for each skill.

<p>MAIN TASKS (DESCRIBE THE MAIN ACTIVITIES):</p> <p>CREATE UI/UX DESIGNING AND PROTOTYPING FOR THE MAIN WEBSITE ON THE WEBSITE TRANSFER PROJECT.</p>	<p>CREATING UI/UX DESIGN AND PROTOTYPING FOR THE MAIN WEBSITE ON THE WEBSITE TRANSFER PROJECT INVOLVES RESEARCHING USER NEEDS, DEFINING CLEAR OBJECTIVES, AND COLLABORATING WITH STAKEHOLDERS TO GATHER REQUIREMENTS. THIS PROCESS INCLUDES DESIGNING INTUITIVE WIREFRAMES, DEVELOPING INTERACTIVE PROTOTYPES, AND ENSURING SEAMLESS USER EXPERIENCE. THE GOAL IS TO CREATE A VISUALLY APPEALING AND FUNCTIONAL WEBSITE THAT ENHANCES USER ENGAGEMENT AND MEETS THE PROJECT'S OBJECTIVES EFFICIENTLY.</p>
<p>LEARN BASIC HTML/CSS AND HAVE LAB EXERCISES FOR ASSESSMENT.</p>	<p>LEARNING BASIC HTML/CSS INVOLVES UNDERSTANDING THE STRUCTURE AND STYLING OF WEB PAGES, COVERING TOPICS SUCH AS HTML ELEMENTS, ATTRIBUTES, AND CSS PROPERTIES. PRACTICAL LAB EXERCISES ARE USED TO REINFORCE THESE CONCEPTS, ALLOWING LEARNERS TO APPLY THEIR KNOWLEDGE BY CREATING AND STYLING WEB PAGES. ASSESSMENTS THROUGH THESE EXERCISES HELP EVALUATE THEIR UNDERSTANDING AND PROFICIENCY IN HTML/CSS.</p>
<p>CREATE IMPROVEMENTS FOR THE USER INTERFACE ON CURRENTLY DEPLOYED WEBSITES AND APPLICATIONS.</p>	<p>CREATING IMPROVEMENTS FOR USER INTERFACE ON CURRENTLY DEPLOYED WEBSITES AND APPLICATIONS INVOLVES ANALYZING USER FEEDBACK AND PERFORMANCE METRICS TO IDENTIFY AREAS OF ENHANCEMENT. THIS PROCESS INCLUDES REDESIGNING ELEMENTS TO IMPROVE USABILITY, UPDATING VISUAL DESIGNS FOR A MODERN LOOK, AND ENSURING CONSISTENT AND INTUITIVE USER EXPERIENCE ACROSS ALL DEVICES. THE GOAL IS TO ENHANCE USER SATISFACTION AND ENGAGEMENT THROUGH TARGETED UI IMPROVEMENTS.</p>
<p>LEARN ABOUT THE WORDPRESS PLATFORM AND THE LARAVEL FRAMEWORK.</p>	<p>LEARNING ABOUT THE WORDPRESS AND WEBFLOW PLATFORM AND THE LARAVEL FRAMEWORK INVOLVES UNDERSTANDING THEIR CORE FUNCTIONALITIES AND APPLICATIONS. FOR WORDPRESS, THIS INCLUDES MASTERING CONTENT MANAGEMENT, THEME CUSTOMIZATION, AND PLUGIN INTEGRATION. FOR LARAVEL, IT INVOLVES LEARNING ITS MVC ARCHITECTURE, ROUTING, AND DATABASE MANAGEMENT. THIS KNOWLEDGE ENABLES DEVELOPERS TO EFFECTIVELY BUILD AND MANAGE DYNAMIC WEBSITES AND WEB APPLICATIONS USING THESE POWERFUL TOOLS.</p>
<p>ATTEND MEETINGS FOR THE WEBSITE TRANSFER ALIGNMENT.</p>	<p>ATTENDING MEETINGS FOR WEBSITE TRANSFER ALIGNMENT INVOLVES ACTIVELY PARTICIPATING IN DISCUSSIONS TO ENSURE THAT ALL STAKEHOLDERS ARE ALIGNED ON PROJECT GOALS, TIMELINES, AND REQUIREMENTS. THIS INCLUDES CLARIFYING DESIGN AND FUNCTIONALITY EXPECTATIONS, ADDRESSING TECHNICAL CONSIDERATIONS, AND COORDINATING TASKS BETWEEN TEAMS TO ENSURE A SMOOTH TRANSITION. EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION AND COLLABORATION DURING THESE MEETINGS ARE CRUCIAL FOR SUCCESSFUL PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION AND MEETING BUSINESS OBJECTIVES.</p>
<p>DAILY ACTIVITY REPORTING.</p>	<p>DAILY ACTIVITY REPORTING INVOLVES DOCUMENTING AND SUMMARIZING THE TASKS, PROGRESS, AND ACHIEVEMENTS ACCOMPLISHED WITHIN A WORKDAY</p>

You may add rows if necessary.

<p>KNOWLEDGE/SKILLS/COMPETENCIES TO BE LEARNED IN THE MAIN AREAS OF GENERAL PROFESSIONALISM, PROGRAMMING, TESTING/QA AND/OR SYSTEMS ANALYSIS. PLEASE FEEL FREE TO ADD OTHER SKILLS BASED ON THE TASKS ASSIGNED.</p>	<p>ESTIMATED TRAINING HOURS (IF APPLICABLE):</p>
<p>WIREFRAMING & PROTOTYPING</p>	<p>200</p>
<p>BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF HTML/CSS</p>	<p>100</p>

KNOWLEDGE OF UI ELEMENTS AND RESPONSIVENESS	50
DEVELOPER COLLABORATION ON WORDPRESS	250

SCHEDULE OF ACTIVITIES:

SCHEDULE (40 hours per week)	ACTIVITIES	EXPECTED RESULTS/OUTCOMES
	Wireframing and Prototyping	To effectively produce a digital prototype and a wireframe on a desired editing tool, as well as to have it as a preview before the generation of the website.
	Train on Basic HTML and CSS	To familiarize with basic knowledge and understanding on coding front-end designing using HTML and CSS.
	Website Transfer Collaboration on WordPress or WebFlow	To effectively produce the main website with healthy collaboration with the team members involved in the project.
	Alignment Meeting and Reporting	To submit and document reports of task completion and progress as well as to brainstorm. This is towards concerns, issues, problems, clarifications regarding the weekly activities done.
	Learn Basic Laravel and make UI improvements on current applications	To familiarize on the workflow and the coding flow on the Laravel Framework. This makes it possible to manage currently deployed applications and improve the look and feel through the front-end codes.

Part 4: Signatures:

All parties agree to provide or obtain training for the skills outlined in this Training Plan.

Laryze Lo Lozano

Student's Name
(signature above printed name)

Joshua Rene Mariano
UAS PHILIPPINES

Internship Supervisor
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Melinda dP Bandalaria
UP Open University Chancellor
(signature above printed name)

Asst. Professor Luisa Gelisan
MMS/200 Adviser for Laryze
Lozano
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Emek Amoloza
UPOU-FICS BAMS Program Chair
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Diego Maranan
Dean, UP Open University Faculty
of Information and Communication
Studies, BAMS MMS 200
Coordinator
(signature above printed name)

B. Internship Acceptance Letter

UNIVERSAL ACCESS AND SYSTEMS SOLUTIONS

109 Reliance Center Building, #99 E. Rodriguez Jr. Ave. (C5), Pasig City, Metro Manila
PHILIPPINES

Email : victori@uas.com.ph
Tel. No.: (02) 667-0862
Website : www.uas.com.ph

INTERNSHIP ACCEPTANCE LETTER

Dear **Laryze Lozano**,

I am pleased to extend an offer for the internship position at Universal Access and System Solutions. After careful consideration of your qualifications, we are impressed with your skills and believe that your background aligns well with the goals and values of our organization.

As an intern with Universal Access and System Solutions, you will have the opportunity to contribute to meaningful projects and gain hands-on experience in the field of Information Technology. Your role will involve collaborating with our talented team to address challenges and develop innovative solutions.

We are confident that your unique skills and perspective will make a valuable contribution to our team. Your internship with Universal Access and System Solutions aims to provide a rich learning experience and exposure to real-world projects.

Please review this offer carefully, and if you decide to accept, please sign, and return a copy of this letter. If you have any questions or need further clarification, feel free to contact me at my email address, kcorvera@uas.com.ph and contact me at 09566870812.

Congratulations, and we hope you accept this offer to embark on an enriching internship experience with us.

Sincerely,

KEVIN CORVERA
Head of Talent Acquisition
Universal Access and System Solutions

ACCEPTED BY:

Laryze Lozano

C. Internship Evaluation Form

INTERNSHIP EVALUATION FORM			
Intern's Name :	Laryze C. Lozano	Internship Start Date :	August 19, 2024
Company :	Universal Access & Systems Solutions Inc.	Internship End Date :	December 4, 2024
Dept. Deployed :	Bus. Innovation and Digital Solutions	Completion of Form Date :	November 20, 2024
Supervisor's Name:	Mr. Joshua Rene Mariano	Total Training Hours:	600 Hours
Work Schedule :	Weekdays - 9:00 AM - 6:00 PM (12:00 PM - 1:00 PM Lunch Break)		

SUMMARY

BUSINESS STRATEGY	WEIGHT	FINAL RATING	OVERALL SCORE
KNOWLEDGE AND APPLICATION OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES	35%	35.00%	100.00%
UI/UX DESIGN SKILLS AND APPLICATION	35%	35.00%	
COMPETENCIES IN PROJECT CONTRIBUTION AND COLLABORATION	30%	30.00%	
TOTAL	100%		

MMS 200 Terminal Evaluation

Knowledge and Application of Multimedia Technologies

During the internship/OJT placement, to what extent did the student demonstrate the competencies which the BAMS program aims to develop in students?

Objective	Target	Weight	Rating	Remarks
Demonstrates understanding of various multimedia information and communication technologies	Successfully integrate and utilize at least three different multimedia technologies in projects, with no major issues reported.	25%	5	Exemplary integration of multiple multimedia technologies, successfully utilizing a combination of tools and platforms with no major issues reported. Demonstrates a strong understanding of how these technologies interconnect to achieve project goals.
Applies current multimedia trends and best practices in their work	Incorporate at least three current multimedia trends or best practices into projects, as evaluated by peer or supervisor reviews.	25%	5	Consistently incorporates the latest multimedia trends and adheres to industry best practices. Peers and supervisors regularly commend the work for being both innovative and effective in applying these trends.
Understand the principles of UI/UX design and their application.	Apply UI/UX principles effectively in 90% of design projects, with positive feedback from users and stakeholders.	25%	5	Exhibits a deep understanding of UI/UX principles, applying them effectively in design projects with overwhelmingly positive feedback from users and stakeholders. Demonstrates a keen eye for user-
Show creativity and innovation in multimedia solutions and content creation.	Present innovative solutions or content in at least two major projects or assignments, with recognition from peers or supervisors for creativity.	25%	5	Has created responsive code ideas in two major projects (MHD and UAS Website) and presented sensible prototypes for user experience. Modern design and animation solutions are also included in this matter
Total Grade		100%	35% / 35%	

UI/UX Design Skills and Application

During the internship/OJT placement, to what extent did the student demonstrate the competencies which the BAMS program aims to develop in UI/UX design?

Objective	Target	Weight	Rating	Remarks
Creates user-friendly and visually appealing interface designs.	Achieve a user satisfaction rating of 85% or higher on design feedback	30%	5	Fast and Reliable, the layout made in both website and prototype are aligned with the branding of the company. Has successfully captured the profile of what the company and its theme are.
Develops effective prototypes that clearly communicate design concept	Complete 90% of prototypes with no major revisions required during stakeholder review.	25%	5	User feel and experience is prioritized in the layout of the Figma prototype designs, there has no revisions but change request for additional feature has been initiated upon review.
Shows proficiency in relevant software (e.g., Figma, WordPress, WebFlow).	Demonstrate advanced skills in at least two of the listed tools, with no significant issues reported in project reviews.	30%	5	Output in Figma and Webflow is sublime, exactly how the client wants it to be presented both in prototype and website.
Shows proficiency in HTML and CSS and delivers proper coding etiquette.	Maintain a code quality score of 75% or higher in code reviews, following best practices and coding standards.	15%	5	Code structure and quality in CSS and HTML shows confidence and techniques from scratch, vanilla, up to libraries. Adaptive and flexible in most solutions.
Total Grade		100%	35% / 35%	

Competencies in Project Contribution and Collaboration

During the internship/OJT placement, to what extent did the student apply skills which a senior undergraduate student from any discipline is expected to possess?

Objective	Target	Weight	Rating	Remarks
Contributes fresh perspectives and innovative ideas	Present at least two new ideas or perspectives in each major project, with at least one idea implemented or acknowledged as valuable.	25%	5	Prototype and solutions are ingenious and modern, these enabled more options for workaround in case of conflicts. She brainstormed with the Team to plan out the website process & alternative designs.
Incorporate their supervisor's feedback to enhance the quality of their work and/or improve their workflow.	Act on 100% of actionable feedback received from supervisors, demonstrating improvement in work quality or workflow efficiency in subsequent projects.	25%	5	Supervisor's suggestions and feedback are effective upon discussion. This made the workflow optimal and has been evident since project startup. Revisions was done ahead of time.
Collaborates effectively with the project team that communicates ideas and concepts clearly	Achieve a team collaboration rating of 85% or higher in peer reviews, with clear and effective communication noted in project evaluations.	25%	5	Communication towards other team members are clear and considerate. Ideas and concepts are discussed in an established manner, leading to flawless execution on implementation.
Delivers work that meets or exceeds project requirements within given deadlines.	100% completion of UI/UX tasks within the allocated days	25%	5	Laryze is very easy to work with and shows respect to her team. Tasks and deliverables are completed ahead of the set deadlines, giving the team extra time to address unexpected errors, make improvements, and implement changes as needed.
Total Grade		100%	30% / 30%	

RATING GUIDE

PERFORMANCE RATING	RATING DESCRIPTION
5 - OUTSTANDING PERFORMANCE	Exceptional results. Successfully achieves all established goals and objectives and significantly exceeds expectations for quality, impact on the business, and/or turnaround time. Capabilities far exceed the knowledge and skills required in the field.
4 - EXCEEDS EXPECTATION	Successfully achieves all established goals and objectives and significantly exceeds expectations for quality, impact on the business, and/or turnaround time. Capabilities far exceed the knowledge and skills required in the job.
3 - SOLID PERFORMANCE	Meets expectations. Solid value-added performance. Demonstrate the knowledge, skills and behaviors required in the job. Effectively and efficiently handles assigned duties and responsibilities. Successfully achieves goals and objectives.
2 - IMPROVEMENT REQUIRED	Below expectation. Meets some but not all expectations on the job.
1 - UNSATISFACTORY PERFORMANCE	Consistently fails to meet job requirements

Intern's Details

Laryze Co Lozano
Student's Name
(signature above printed name)

Prepared and Evaluated by:

Joshua Rene Mariano
Internship Supervisor
(signature above printed name)

Nadine Faye Alarcon
Creatives Head & Coordinator
(signature above printed name)

Received by:

Asst. Professor Luisa Gelisan
MMS 200 Adviser for Laryze Lozano
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Emely Amolosa
UPOU-FICS BAMS Program Chair
(signature above printed name)

Dr. Diego Maranan
Dean, UP Open University Faculty of Information and
Communication Studies, BAMS MMS 200 Coordinator
(signature above printed name)

D. OJT Certificate of Completion

CERTIFICATE OF INTERNSHIP

December 4, 2024

This is to certify that **LARYZE C. LOZANO**, student of **UNIVERSEITY OF THE PHILIPPINES- OPEN UNIVERSITY**, has successfully completed the **600 hours internship** in the field of **BUSINESS INNOVATION AND DIGITAL SOLUTIONS** from **August 19, 2024 to December 4, 2024** under the guidance of **JOSHUA MARIANO, Networks Engineer**.

Issued this 4th day of December 2024 at 108-109 IT Reliance Building E Rodriguez Pasig City.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'K. Corvera', written over a faint circular watermark.

KEVIN CORVERA
Head of Talent Acquisition

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'C. Flores', written over a faint circular watermark.

CATHERINE FLORES
Human Resources Business Partner

Validated By:

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'J. Mariano', written over a faint circular watermark.

JOSHUA MARIANO
Networks Engineer
Business Innovation and Digital Solutions

A 108-109 Reliance IT Center Building, 99 E. Rodriguez Jr. Ave.,
Pasig City Metro Manila, Philippines
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